

ATHOR Newsletter – the Team is Now Complete!

Reminder

As an initiative of the FIRE network in 2016, ATHOR is a 4-year Innovative Training Network Project dedicated to the Advanced Thermomechanical multiscale modelling of Refractory linings.

Launched in October 2017 and funded by the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions of the Horizon 2020 European Program, ATHOR is coordinated by IRCER (University of Limoges/FR).

Last International PhD Recruitment

Most of the students joined the network during 2018 with the last PhD position at Uni. Minho/PT being filled in February 2019. With Thais Soares joining ATHOR from Brazil, now is the perfect time to introduce ATHOR's complete Early Stage Researcher (ESR) team.

ATHOR Training Events and Site Visits during the Past Nine Months

Research Training Courses (RTC)

- RTC1-Part 1: Leoben – June 2018
Fracture Mechanics (25 Pers.)
- RTC1-Part 2: Aachen – October 2018
Corrosion (36 Pers.)
- RTC2-Part 1: Orléans – January 2019
Thermomechanical Modelling (39 Pers.)

Site Visits (SV)

- SV 1 and SV 2: Leoben – June 2018
RHI-Magnesita Veitsch Plant
RHI-Magnesita TCL
- SV 3: IJmuiden – October 2018
Tata Steel Plant
- SV 4: Orléans – January 2019
DURALEX Glass Plant

The Training Event RTC2-Part 1, Thermo-mechanical Modelling, included courses on computational plasticity, application of FEM modelling in industry and thermomechanical properties and modelling of fused-cast refractories. Debutants and advanced users were also able to improve their modelling skills with Abaqus.

First Award for an ATHOR ESR

RTC1-Part 2 was organised in conjunction with the 61st International Colloquium on Refractories (ICR) 2018 in Aachen/DE. One of ATHOR's students, Lucas Teixeira, already gained the 3rd Place in the ICR Poster Competition (only 6 months after starting his PhD). Furthermore, the first ATHOR publication has been accepted in a rank peer-reviewed scientific journal.

First Secondment Periods for ESRs

While training and site visits all around Europe are an important part of the ATHOR program, the students are also managing to advance their research. Six of the students are currently doing/completed secondments and four (Ilona Kieliba, Vahid Tadaion, Farid Asadi and Camille Reynaert) have received scholarships from the JECS Trust.

Next ATHOR Steps

The next ATHOR Training Event will take place in June 2019, in Cavailon/FR, and will include site visits at Saint-Gobain SEFPRO Plant (Le-Pontet) and Alteo Plant (Gardanne). This Training Event will follow ATHOR's participation at the Summer School on Corrosion and at the ECerS Con-

ference in Turin/IT. We look forward to seeing you there!

You can also follow ATHOR on:

- www.etn-athor.eu
- facebook.com/etnathor
- twitter.com/etnathor
- linkedin.com/company/etnathor

Diana VITIELLO (Italy)
Uni. Limoges (France)

Robert KACZMAREK (Poland)
Uni. Limoges (France)

Farid ASADI (Iran)
Uni. Limoges (France)

Camille REYNAERT (France)
AGH Krakow (Poland)

Ilona KIELIBA (Poland)
RWTH Aachen (Germany)

Efstathios KYRILIS (Greece)
RWTH Aachen (Germany)

Vahid TADAION (Iran)
RWTH Aachen (Germany)

Thanh NGUYEN (Vietnam)
Uni. Leoben (Austria)

Lucas TEIXEIRA (Brazil)
Uni. Orléans (France)

Mahmoud ALI (Egypt)
Uni. Orléans (France)

Rafael OLIVEIRA (Brazil)
Uni. Coimbra (Portugal)

Sina DARBAN (Iran)
AGH Krakow (Poland)

Thais SOARES (Brazil)
Uni. Minho (Portugal)

Soheil SAMADI (Iran)
Uni. Leoben (Austria)

Pratik GAJJAR (India)
Uni. Minho (Portugal)

Fig. 3 PhD students during the ATHOR Training Session in Orléans (January 2019)